

A Study of William James' Pragmatism

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Abstract

This paper will discuss the pragmatism of William James is an attempt to solve the problem 'Why need the theory of truth for social problem?' (Research Problem) The answer to this question will be provided by showing that human society needs not only the truth is relative but also practical consequences to human purpose and evaluation. (Tentative Solution) This paper will contribute to the criterion of truth in James' theory and truth is what works or has good experimental results. It is necessary for the practical life in human society. (Contribution)

Key Words: Pragmatic, Relative, Truth.

Introduction

Contemporary Western Philosophy can also be seen as a movement against Hegel's Absolute Idealism. Hegel's philosophy was most popular in the west during the nineteenth century. But with the turn of the century people found it to be no longer acceptable.

There are many reasons for its unpopularity and the most total one is that it cannot hold good in practical life. According to Hegel, the Absolute perfect, flawless, it is dynamic, very active. It is not moving in all directions but going one way, that is, towards progress.

However, in the early part of the twentieth century, there are many bad situations all over the world. But if the Absolute were perfect as Hegel has claimed, how can we say with Hegel that reality is always moving towards progress? The result is people begin to doubt the reliability of Hegel's philosophy.

Many new theories in science that arise in the early part of the present century are also responsible for Hegel's philosophy to become unpopular. For example, in physics we have quantum theory by max planet, indeterminacy theory by Heisenberg and theory of relativity by Einstein.

One of the greatest achievements in the twentieth century is the rapid development of symbolic and mathematical logic. Because of it, we come to have many new and practical methods of analysis in hand. Philosophers today are usually trained in these methods and they apply these methods extensively in trying to analyze the value of the philosophy.

Extensive use of the method of analysis is another general characteristic of present day philosophy. To be able to use this method extensively, mathematical logic and symbolic logic have developed rapidly in the present century. Many new theories in science that arise in the early part of the present century are also responsible for Hegel's philosophy to become a popular. Some of the philosophical systems that have arisen in History are studied analytically as to whether they are logical or consistent, what the premise or premises assumed are, and what conclusions have been drawn from the premises for instance, G.E. Moore makes and attempt to analyze Berkeley's subjective idealism with the help of the analytic method. Consequently the present age is called "the age of Analysis".

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Linguistic analysis comes to be another general characteristic of today's philosophy. In fact, analysis of language, especially the English language, becomes a major occupation of twentieth century thinkers such as Ludwig Wittgenstein.

Contemporary philosophy is also characterized by its great emphasis on man. As a result there are many varieties of humanism in this period. For example, existentialism, pragmatism, and so forth are all various forms of humanistic philosophy.

Chapter I

A Study of William James' Pragmatism

1.1. The Role of "Pragmatism"

Pragmatism is an important philosophical movement, in the twentieth century. Pragmatism is a uniquely American Philosophy. In general all the Pragmatist content that philosophy as a technical concern must bear on life, that is on the life of common sense and common man. According to them, if a philosophy does not have any bearing on life, then it is not a philosophy but a mere verbal dispute.

Pragmatism is both a method and a theory of truth. It can be used by thinkers holding widely different views because its function is chiefly that of setting metaphysical disputes. Metaphysical arguments on close analysis are usually found to involve notions or ideas about which one can always ask whether they lead to any practical consequences. According to the pragmatists, an idea must be shown to make a difference in Practical life, it is to be meaningful.

In the true spirit of contemporary thinking pragmatism also began as a sharp reaction against all forms of idealism and absolutism. During the later years of the nineteenth century and the early part of the twentieth century William James and John Dewey in American and F.C.S. Schiller in Great Britain deviated from the traditional approach of philosophy and proposed pragmatic modes of thought.

Pragmatism, as a philosophical attitude and a method is opposed to purely logical and intellectual bias of philosophy; its approach is essentially practical and human. Philosophy, according to a pragmatist, is vitally related to human life and existence. Our concepts and theories are useless if they have no relation with practical life and the problems connected with it. Pragmatism is a practical philosophy based on relativity of values.

Everything, including knowledge and truth is to be determined by human considerations and utility. Rejecting logic at traditional philosophy as barren intellectual exercise, pragmatism holds that our thought process must not be divorced from practical life. It is practical utility in life that determines truth and reality. Absolute truth is figment of logicians is of no importance in practice.

All truths are manmade and therefore human considerations are the only basis on which truth or falsity of our beliefs depends. The basic principle of pragmatism states that our ideas and beliefs are means for reorganizing experience and hence guides for action. Man possesses the most practical faculty in the form of mind and it must be used in finding ways to solve our problems and for improving conditions of life. The function of thought is not to understand the world as it is but to find how to change it so to serve human purpose.

Making radical departure from the history of thought pragmatism holds that truth pertains to thoughts which help people to succeed in action. Deriving inspiration from the British empiricism pragmatic thinkers preferred to avoid speculative thinking and made human experience and utility the sole test of truth and reality. Pragmatists never claim to have evolved a new philosophy; they only profess to have given a method and approach derived from natural

sciences which can be applied to philosophy. For this reason theirs is a great contribution to the contemporary philosophical thinking.

Coming to the protagonists of this new approach, Charles S. Peirce (1839-1914), an American thinker, used the term pragmatism for the first time in 1878 in his article "How to make our ideas clear." According to him for knowing, meaning an intellectual conception we should find out the possible practical consequences from accepting the truth of that concept. Pragmatism is to be used as a method and technique for knowing the meaning of concepts. All knowledge is developing, growing through experiences and there is possibility of attaining absolute certainly, absolute truth.

The purpose of this article is to define the principle theories of the philosophical movements known under the names of Pragmatism, Instrumentalism, or Experimentalism. To do this we must trace their historical development; for this method seems to present the simplest way of comprehending these movements and at the same time avoids certain current misunderstandings of their doctrines and of their aims.

The origin of Pragmatism goes back to Charles Sanders Peirce, the son of one of the most celebrated mathematicians of the United States, and himself very proficient in the science of mathematics; he is one of the founders of the modern symbolic logic of relations. Unfortunately Peirce was not at all a systematic writer and never expounded his ideas in a single system. The pragmatic method which he developed applies only to a very narrow and limited universe of discourse. After William James had extended the scope of the method, Peirce wrote an exposition of the origin of pragmatism as he had first conceived it; it is from this exposition that we take the following passages.

The term "pragmatic", contrary to the opinion of those who regard pragmatism as an exclusively American conception, was suggested to him by the study of Kant. In the *Metaphysic* of Marls Kant established a distinction between pragmatic and practical. The latter term applies to moral laws which Kant regards a priori, whereas the former term applies to the rules of art and technique which are based on experience and are applicable to experience. Peirce, who was an empiricist, with the habits of mind, as he put it, of the laboratory, consequently refused to call his system "practicals" as some of his friends suggested. As a logician he was interested in the art and technique of real thinking and especially as far as pragmatic method is concerned in the art of making concepts clear, or of construing adequate and effective definitions in accord with the spirit of scientific method.

Following his own words, for a person "who still thought in Kantian terms most readily and 'pragmatism' was as far apart as the two poles; the former belonging in a region of thought where no mind of the experimental type can ever make sure of solid ground under his feet, the latter expressing relation to some definite human purpose. Now quite the most striking feature of the new theory was its recognition of an inseparable connection between rational cognition and rational purpose."

In alluding to the experimental type of mind, we are brought to the exact meaning given by Peirce to the word "pragmatic". In speaking of an experimentalist as a man whose intelligence is formed in the laboratory, he said: "Whatever assertion you may make to him, he will either understand as meaning that, if a given prescription for an experiment ever can be and ever is carried out in act, an experience of a given description will result, else he will see no sense at all in what you say." And thus Peirce developed the theory that "the rational purport of a word or other expression, lies exclusively in its conceivable bearing upon the conduct of life; so that, since obviously nothing that might not result from experiment can have any direct bearing upon conduct, if one can define accurately all the conceivable experimental phenomena which the affirmation or denial of a concept could imply, one will have therein a complete definition of the concept.

The essay in which Peirce developed his theory bears the title: "How to Make Our Ideas Clear." There is a remarkable similarity here to Kant's doctrine in the efforts which he made to interpret the universality of concepts in the domain of experience in the same way in which Kant established the law of practical reason in the domain of the a priori. "The rational meaning of every proposition lies in the future --- But of the myriads of forms into which a proposition may be translated, what is that one which is to be called its very meaning? It is, according to the pragmatist, that form in which the proposition becomes applicable to human conduct, not in these or those special circumstances, nor when one entertains this or that special design, but that form which is most directly applicable to self-control under every situation, and to every purpose." So also, "the pragmatist does not make to consist in action, but makes it to consist in that process of evolution whereby the existent comes more and more to embody generals..." – in other words- the process whereby the existent becomes, with the aid of action, a body of rational tendencies or of habits generalized as much as possible. These statements of Peirce are quite conclusive with respect to two errors which are commonly committed in regard to the ideas of the founder of pragmatism. It is often said of pragmatism that it subordinates thought and rational activity to particular ends of interest and profit. It is true that the theory according to Peirce's conception implies essentially a certain relation to action, to human conduct. But the role of action is that of an intermediary. In order to be able to attribute a meaning to concepts, one must be able to apply them to existence. Now it is by means of action that this application is made possible. And the modification of existence which results from this application constitutes the true meaning of concepts.

Pragmatism is, therefore, far from being that glorification of action for its own sake which is regarded as the peculiar characteristic of American life. It is also to be noted that there is a scale of possible applications of concepts to existence, and hence a diversity of meanings. The greater the extension of the concepts, the more they are freed from the restrictions which limit them to particular cases, the more is it possible for us to attribute the most general meaning to a term. Thus the theory of Peirce is opposed to every restriction of the meaning of a concept to the achievement of a particular end, and still more to a personal aim. It is still more strongly opposed to the idea that reason or thought should be reduced to being a servant of any interest which is pecuniary or too narrow. This theory was American in its origin in so far as it insisted on the necessity of human conduct and the fulfillment of some in order to clarify thought. But at the same time, it disapproves of those aspects of American life which make action an end in itself, and which conceive ends too narrowly and too practically. In considering a system of philosophy in its relation to national factors it is necessary to keep in mind not only the aspects of life which are incorporated in the system, but also the aspects against which the system is protest. There never was a philosopher who has merited the name for the simple reason that he glorified the tendencies and characteristics of his social environment; just as it is also true that there never has been a philosopher who has not seized upon certain aspects of the life of his time and idealized them.

The work commenced by Peirce was continued by William James. In one sense James narrowed the application of Peirce's pragmatic method, but at the same time he extended it. The articles which Peirce wrote in 1878 commanded almost no attention from philosophical circles, which were then under the dominating influence of the neo-Kantian idealism of Green, and of the Oxford School, excepting those circles in which the Scottish philosophy of common sense maintained its supremacy. In 1898 James inaugurated the new pragmatic movement in an address entitled, "Philosophical Conceptions and Practical Results," later reprinted in the volume, *Collected Essays and Reviews*. Even in this early study one can easily notice the presence of those two tendencies to restrict and at the same time to extend early pragmatism. After having quoted the psychological remark of Peirce that "beliefs are really rules for action, and the whole function of thinking is but one step in the production of habits of action," and

that every idea which we frame for ourselves of an object is really an idea of the possible effects of that object, he expressed the opinion that all these principles could be expressed more broadly than Peirce expressed them. "The ultimate test for us of what a truth means is indeed the conduct it dictates or inspires. But it inspires that conduct because it first foretells some particular turn to our experience which shall call for just that conduct from us. And James should prefer to express Peirce's principle by saying that the effective meaning of any philosophic proposition can always be brought down to some particular consequence, in our future practical experience, whether active or passive, the point lying rather in the fact that the experience must be particular, than in the fact that it must be active. "In an essay written in 1908 James repeats this statement and states that whenever he employs the term "the practical," he means by it, "the distinctively concrete, the individual, the particular and effective as opposed to the abstract, general and inert- "Pragmas" are things in their plurality- particular consequences can perfectly well be of a theoretic nature.

1.2. William James' "Pragmatism"

William James (1842-1920), was a American Psychologist and philosopher William James helped to popularize the philosophy of pragmatism with his book pragmatism. (*A New Name for old ways of thinking (1907)*). Theory of meaning and verification developed for scientific hypotheses by American philosopher C.S. Peirce.

Pragmatic philosophy finds its clearest formulation in the ideas of William James. Supporting pierce's view that Pragmatism is a method of making our ideas clear or finding meaningfulness of our concepts. It pierce was the founder of pragmatism and the first to use the name "pragmatism" then it was William James who defended and popularized it and make it an important philosophical movement. It was because of him that Pragmatics came to dominate the American intellectual world. James elaborates these to settle metaphysical, epistemological and moral disputes. Truth and beliefs are to be measured through consequences in life and behavior of a person who holds these. For James, beliefs are only rules for action. William James considered logical and intellectual approach to traditional philosophy as futile. Philosophical problems have necessary implications for making; therefore philosophy must be related to practical life.

James held that truth is what works, or has good experimental results. In a related theory, James argued the existence of God is partly verifiable because many people derive benefits from believing.

James generalized the pragmatic method, developing it from a critique of the logical basis of the science into a basis for the evaluation of all experience. He maintained that the meaning of ideas is found only in terms of their possible consequences. If consequences are lacking, ideas are meaningless.

James contended that this is the method used by scientists to define their terms and to test their hypothesis, which, if meaningful, entail predictions. The hypothesis can be considered true if the predicted events take place. On the other hand, most metaphysical theories are meaningless, because they entail no testable predictions. Meaningful theories, James argued, are instruments for dealing with problems that arise experience.

According to James pragmatism, then, truth is that which works. One determines what works by testing propositions in experience. In so doing, one finds that certain propositions become true. As James put it, "Truth is something that happens to an idea" in the process of its verification. It is not a static property. This does not mean, however, that anything can be true. The true is only the expedient in the way of our thinking, just as "the right" is only the expedient in the way of our behaving," James maintained. One cannot believe whatever one wants to believe, because such self-centered beliefs would not work out.

James also used the Pragmatic idea to define the nature of truth, thus giving a new interpretation of the old coherence and correspondence theories of truth. The purpose of this article is to define the principle theories of the philosophical movements known under the names of pragmatism. To do this we must trace their historical development; for this method seems to present the simplest way of comprehending these movements and at the same time avoids certain current miss understandings of their doctrines and of their aims.

James inaugurated the new pragmatic movement in an address entitled, 'Philosophical Conceptions and Practical Results and. Later reprinted in the volume, collected Essays Reviews. Even in this early study one can easily notice the presence of those two tendencies to restrict and at the same time to extend early pragmatism.

William James alluded to the development which he gave to Peirce's expression of the principle. In one sense one can say that he enlarged the bearing of the principle by the substitution of particular consequences. But another sense this substitution limited the application of the principle since it destroyed the importance attached by Peirce to the greatest possible application of the rule, or the habit of conduct its extension to universality.

James there alludes to the use of a method of determining the meaning of truth. Since truth is a term and has consequently a meaning, this extension is a legitimate application of Pragmatic method. But it should be remarked that here this method serves only to make clean the meaning of the term, and has nothing to do with the truth of a particular Judgment. The principle reason which led James to give a new color to pragmatic method was that he was preoccupied with applying the method to determine the meaning of philosophical problems and questions and that moreover, he chose to submit to examination philosophical notions of a theological or religious nature. He wished to establish a criteria which would enable one to determine whether a given philosophical questions has an authentic and vital meaning of whether, on the contrary it was trivial and purely verbal; and in the farmer case, what interests were at stake, when one accepts and affirms one or the other of two theses in dispute. James was an educator and wished to force the general public to realize that certain problems, certain philosophical debates have a real importance for mankind, because the beliefs which they bring in to play lead to very different modes of conduct. If this important distinction is not grasped, it is impossible to understand the majority of the ambiguities and errors which belong to the later period in the pragmatic movement.

James took as an example the controversy between theism and materialism. It follows from this principle that if the course of the world is considered as completed, it is equally legitimate to assert that God or matter was it cause whether one way the other, the facts are what they are and it is they which determine what ever meaning is to be given to their cause. . God them has the meaning of a power concerned with assuming the triumph of ideal and spiritual values and matter becomes a power indifferent to the triumph or defeat of these values.

From the point of view of James an educator or of a student or it you will of those who are thoroughly interested in these problems, in philosophical discussions and controversies, there is no reason for contesting the value of this application of pragmatic method, but it is no less important to determine the nature of this application. It affords a means of discovering the implications from human life of philosophical conceptions for human life of philosophical conceptions which are often treated as of no importance and of a purely dialectical nature. It furnished a criterion for determining the vital implication of belts which present themselves as alternatives in any theory. Thus as James said that whole function of philosophy has this aim, it seems that he is referring rather to the teaching than to the construction of philosophy. So that there remains only to define the consequences which are reflected in life by the acceptance of one or the other of these formulas as true.

James holds that truth is not something in the nature of things; it is discovered by successful action. For example, a belief is true if it works in actual experience and produces beneficial results. Apart from theory of meaning, James developed pragmatism as a theory of truth. Any idea that helps in our experience so far as linking one part of it with another and working satisfactorily is to be taken as true. It is to become an instrument of successful action and experience. Truth and falsity of a proposition depends on how far it fulfills our purpose and satisfies our emotional and physical needs.

A false proposition produces failure and disappointment. In this way the real test of a theory, a belief or a concept is the effect of it on us and the practical result. Test of truth is a practical consequence. Thus truth is not an end in itself but a means of satisfaction of needs. Similarly knowledge is not for the sake of knowledge but a means for life and solving of specific problems. A concept is said to be true because it is useful. Whatever is true must field maximum satisfaction. In the view of James even if the hypothesis of God works satisfactory it is true. Truth is useful and advantageous. Truth has no value except that it helps in reaching our objective. It is an extrinsic good. Thus truth is not found but made.

William James disagreed with the ways traditional disputes between determinism and indeterminism between materialism and idealism, between monism and pluralism have been sorted out. The real question is what difference it makes in our experience if we accept one or the other view. For example, indeterminism is more beneficial as for consequences since it implies the real possibilities in the world than necessities. Man must determine his actions assuming himself above causal law. He must assume his freedom to determine his actions which in turn prove effective in creating the world of his liking. Our aim is to improve our life while determinism makes man subservient of outside factors and thus passive. Besides this, in the pragmatism of James a surprising aspect is found in his tolerance for non-scientific ways of thinking. He demonstrated pragmatic value of theism since it brings inner peace and develops a definite attitude to life.

James offered two examples, the first is an argument in which the question is whether one can say that a man "goes round" a squirrel if he circles a tree around whose trunk the squirrel is also moving. James shows that the key-words here is the word "round" it "going round" means that the man is in successive places to north, east, south and west of the squirrels, then he does go round the animal. But if "going round" means that the man is behind, then to the right then in front of and then to the left of the squirrel, then he may not go round the animal, because it may be moving simultaneously with his movement. So, an argument of this kind is nothing but a verbal one. What James is trying to say is that many of the philosophical disputes are nothing but verbal ones and thus they can be resolved through careful analysis.

As a method of truth James claims that pragmatism favors the utilitarian emphasis on what is useful and the positivists, dislike of metaphysical speculation and merely verbal solutions of problems.

According to James an idea is true if it permits the one who accepts it to have "satisfactory relations with other parts of our experience". An idea is accepted as true if it answers to that conditions, but that does not mean that it will be accepted forever as true. It is true for that particular specified situation but at least in principle it is subject to change modifications and revision, sometimes new and unexpected conditions may call for a complete rejection of the idea in question. So the truth of an idea depends on the context in which it has been used. This contextual theory of truth is sometimes misinterpreted as meaning everybody may believe whether happens to make him comfortable. Actually James has set down some definite conditions that an idea must satisfy so as to be accepted as workable and hence as true. First of all, an idea must be consistent with other ideas, comfortable to existing facts, and

subject to experiential corroboration and validation. But one thing is certain he does reject the idea of Truth.

James tries to apply the pragmatic method to some age-old problems in philosophy. Thus, for instance, he tries to apply it to the problem of substance, how the thing-attribute aspect of grammar has misled philosophers to the concept of an underlying "substance". The problem of evil, that of free will and determinism, merits and demerits of materialism and spiritualism are also analysed.

Conclusion

Pragmatism is a philosophy which has aroused people's interest in the twentieth century. In the western world its popularity in the twentieth century is great the people accept and study it relating to and reflecting their experience. In general all the pragmatists contend that philosophy as a technical concern must bear on life, that is, on the life of common sense and common man. According to them if a philosophy does not have bearing on life, then it is not a philosophy but a mere verbal dispute.

The problem of the relation between man and society is very important for pragmatists. Pragmatism is both a method and a theory of truth. It can be used by thinkers holding widely different views because its function is chiefly that of settling metaphysical disputes. Metaphysical arguments, on close analysis, are usually found to involve notions or ideas about which one can always ask whether they lead to any practical consequences. According to the pragmatists, experience is the key concept.

. Present day thinkers spend a lot of time studying human society. But they are not satisfied with a mere list of a series of human societies in history. They try to bring out the interrelations between man and society. They always see the two as having an influence upon each other.

According to James pragmatism, then, truth is that which works. One determines what works by testing propositions in experience. In so doing, one finds that certain propositions become true. As James put it, "Truth is something that happens to an idea in the process of its verification; it is not a static property. This does not mean, however, that anything can be true. The true is only the expedient in the way of our thinking, just as the right is only the expedient in the way of our behaving; James maintained one cannot believe whatever one wants to believe, because such self-centered beliefs would not work out.

James was opposed to absolute metaphysical systems and argued against doctrines that describe reality as a unified, monolithic whole. He argued for a pluralistic universe, denying that the world can be explained in terms of an absolute force or scheme that determines the interrelations of things and events. He held that the interrelations, whether they serve to hold things together or apart, are just as real as the things themselves.

Therefore Pragmatism is both a method and a theory of truth. According to the Pragmatists, an idea must be shown to make in practical life. It is to be meaningful. So pragmatism is a practical philosophy based on relativity of values. For James, philosophical problems have necessary implications for making; therefore philosophy must be related to practical life. James held that truth is what works, or has good experimental results. According to James a statement or a concept or an idea is true if it gives happiness, satisfaction, good experimental result in human life. So we can say that James is a humanist's philosopher. It is necessary for the practical life in human society.

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